

Fair, equitable and productive international collaborative research: experiences from 13 research projects

Report from the closing seminar of the research program grant: "Sustainability and Resilience–Tackling consequences of climate and environmental changes". Second cohort of grantees

Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm, Sweden, May 24th-25th 2023

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Group picture day 1, May 24th 2023. Photo: Johannes Ernstberger

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Emilie Lindkvist (Principal Investigator), Tim M. Daw, Elizabeth (Liz) Drury O'Neill, Maria Mancilla García prepared the concept note for the seminar, contributed with the organization of the workshop and provided input and feedback throughout the process. Hanna Wetterstrand was the lead facilitator of the closing seminar and provided input and comments on the draft report. Jineth Berrío Martínez supported the workshop preparation, running and documentation, synthesized information and drafted this report. Oskar Karlsson, Emelie Rietz Liljedahl, Claudia Teutschbein and Josepha Wessels provided feedback and commented on the draft report.

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Executive summary

The closing seminar titled “How can we contribute to International Collaborative Research being Fair and Productive?” focused on better understanding the challenges and recommendations for international collaborative research projects, particularly between low-income and high-income countries. The second cohort of grantees of the research program grant “Sustainability and Resilience – Tackling consequences of climate and environmental changes” participated in this event, representing 13 out of the 16 projects granted in 2018. A total of 18 participants from Sweden-based universities, 15 participants from universities in Africa, South Asia and South America and three participants from Swedish research funding agencies came together for two days at the Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University in Sweden.

Through an iterative process, under Chatham house rules, participants engaged in a series of individual reflections, work in pairs, small groups, and plenary discussions, employing Time to Think and Forum Theater techniques. This process provided participants opportunities to discuss, exchange and reflect on their experiences. The aim was to allow for a deep understanding of challenges to fair, equal and productive partnerships in an open, inclusive and safe space and ground-truth potential solutions with what people have experienced. As a result, participants collectively worked on **guidelines and recommendations for fair, equitable and productive international collaborative research**.

Based on the learnings and experiences from the represented projects, **ten fundamental principles for international collaborative research** were collectively identified such as clear and good communication, open dialogue, and explicitness, transparency and openness in all activities, accountability and availability, flexibility and adaptability and respect of differences and cultural values. In addition to these principles, three main workshop outcomes are presented in this report: 1) **recommendations for funders** related to calls for proposals, funding allocation and the role of funders during project implementation, 2) **a list of recommendations for researchers to navigate the research process** from seeking funding to the closing phase and 3) lists of **challenges to international collaborative research**.

Overall, practical experiences from the projects showed that understanding local contexts, considering others’ perspectives, good communication, open dialogue, clear definition of roles and distribution of tasks and teamwork are crucial ingredients for effective collaborations. Building relationships, trust and capacities while being aware of differences and respecting them are also important aspects within international collaborations. We hope these guidelines can contribute to future collaborations.

Seminar description

How can we contribute to international collaborative research on Sustainability and Resilience being fair, equitable and productive? Four years and a pandemic after the start-up seminar it was timely and valuable to deeply investigate the challenges of international research collaboration across geographic distances, disciplines, cultures and institutions, and jointly develop practical guidance to funders and future collaborators. Therefore, the closing seminar addressed the praxis of collaborative research throughout different research phases focusing on challenges, potential solutions and recommendations. This seminar also provided networking opportunities, fostered dialogue with funding agencies and facilitated dissemination of project outcomes in a poster passageway within the event ([Appendix A1](#) & [Appendix A2](#)).

Building on the solutions posters from the start-up seminar in 2019 (digitized action points in [Appendix A3](#)) and individual input through a pre-workshop survey filled in by participants before arrival ([Appendix A4](#)), the closing seminar was designed to address the following questions: “How did it go? How fair, equitable and productive has the research collaboration been? What aspects were implemented from the start-up seminar? What assumptions have hindered us from building more equitable and productive collaborations? What recommendations should be given to researchers, collaborators and funders, so that international collaborative research projects on Sustainability and Resilience achieve fair, equitable and productive partnerships?” (see the workshop agenda in [Appendix A5](#)).

People involved in collaborative processes face and experience diverse challenges and conflicts. The top three barriers mentioned by participants in the pre-workshop survey were: 1) mobility restrictions, limited in-person meetings & COVID pandemic, 2) unequal contributions to the research process and papers and, 3) limited communication and coordination (full list of barriers in [Appendix A4.3](#)). Building on the challenges identified, the closing seminar provided different opportunities for reflecting as individuals, pairs and groups on collaborative research throughout four different stages of research: 1) developing proposal and seeking/obtaining funding, 2) startup of the research, 3) on-going research and 4) final stages.

There were also opportunities to think and share anonymous reflections by actively using the ten components of a thinking environment¹ and their various applications including thinking pairs, rounds, the Time to Think council and dialogues (Kline 2002). Consequently, interactions through the two-day workshop were based on equity, appreciation and active listening without interrupting, under the guidance of a qualified

¹ Attention, Equality, Ease, Appreciation, Encouragement, Feelings, Information, Difference, Incisive Questions, Place [The Ten Components - Time to Think](#)

facilitator in Time to Think² and the use of Chatham House rules³. Additionally, we used Forum Theater, an art-based tool to interactively ease up the conversation and enable opening up to potentially sensitive topics, understanding them better and thinking deeply about potential solutions. The use of Forum Theater was inspired by the experiences of one of the research projects, and sessions were facilitated by colleagues from Mozambique, Kenya and Sweden.

Forum Theater drew on stories that reflected everyday situations and communicated conflictual or socially complex ideas within international collaborative research processes (see Sullivan and Lloyd 2006; Kumagai et al. 2007; Haider, L.J, 2018). Participants jointly developed scripts to perform, present and discuss four scenes, one scene for each research stage. The use of this tool helped to illustrate different realities, power dynamics and chains of pressure within collaborative projects. During performances, the audience was encouraged to jump into the scene and replace actors at points of frustration or disagreement to suggest their own actions and direct the course of the situations towards more favorable outcomes.

How to guide a researcher to do fair, productive and equitable international research collaboration? By responding to this final question and drawing on the workshop discussions and available inputs (i.e., action list from 2019, pre-workshop survey responses, individual reflections, learnings from the four Forum Theater scenes and list of assumptions from the thinking in pairs exercises), participants prepared six posters in which fundamental guiding principles were illustrated and a step-by-step guide was developed for each research stage. Pictorial analysis was used as a tool to reinforce the descriptions within the posters ([Appendix A6](#)). Finally, information collected during the two-day Sustainability and Resilience (SaR) closing seminar was digitized, organized and synthesized into this report.

² <https://www.timetothink.com/> - a process to facilitate independent thinking and maximize collective intelligence in so-called thinking environments.

³ "Participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed" <https://www.chathamhouse.org/>.

Forum Theater Intro - day 1, May 24th 2023. Photo: Johannes Ernstberger

Principles for international collaborative research

Figure 1. Ten fundamental principles for fair, equitable and productive international collaborative research collectively identified by workshop participants. Workshop pictures illustrate some of the principles being practiced during the SaR closing seminar. Photos: Johannes Ernstberger & Jineth Berrío-Martínez

Through an iterative process, participants collectively identified fundamental and transversal principles for fair, equitable and productive international collaborative research (Figure 1). The ten fundamental principles are: 1) clear and good communication, open dialogue and explicitness, 2) inclusiveness and equity, 3) transparency and openness in all activities, 4) honesty and integrity, 5) mutual trust, 6) accountability and availability, 7) flexibility and adaptability, 8) respect of differences and cultural values, 9) empathy, solidarity, care for each other and humility, 10) reciprocity. Based on practical experiences from 13 research projects, these principles apply to all research-based collaborations and should be practiced by all project team members and collaborators through all phases of research.

During the production of the step-by-step posters, elements that should be in focus for a successful partnership within research projects were recognized (see [Appendix A6](#)). These elements are captured by the ten fundamental principles, which accounts for good leadership, strategic planning including clear project roles, timelines and agreements, teamwork, shared responsibility and compromising, willingness to share and collaborate at all stages, receive and provide feedback, ask for help and have the courage to admit problems, enable co-development and co-production of knowledge, active participation and listening, capacity building and nurture relationships.

Equity in collaboration needs ethics, transparency and leadership⁴

Scene on research stage 1 - working group 1. Photo: Johannes Ernstberger

⁴ Participant's reflection - main take-away from the closing seminar May 24th-25th 2023 (workshop evaluation, response 16)

Recommendations for international funding agencies

How can funders contribute to equitable and fair international research collaboration?

Research funding agencies have a relevant role in fostering and promoting fair, equitable and productive partnerships, at different stages, within the international research projects they support. Funding agencies have different approaches and strategies to manage these aspects, e.g., some adopt more systemic and adaptive approaches, they follow global development, find synergies and build partnerships with other institutions to improve crisis management. Others explicitly work on knowledge development or have calls for specific countries, including countries with non-democratic governments. Some funding agencies request that research proposals are led and reports prepared by researchers from low-income countries, etc. Despite that, there is still room for improvement, particularly, considering challenges that can arise within international collaborative research processes in a changing world.

Considering the experiences from 13 collaborative projects, the SaR closing seminar aimed to further investigate those challenges and think about potential solutions for equal and fair collaborations. Different recommendations and ideas for funders to consider were collectively identified and developed by participants during the Time to Think council exercise in the afternoon of day 1, May 24th, where funders and participants had an open dialogue in plenary and worked in small groups. The following subsections present a list of recommendations in three categories: 1) suggestions linked to calls for proposals, 2) suggestions for funding allocation and utilization and 3) role of funders during project implementation.

Suggestions linked to calls for proposals

- Release/publish the call text minimum six (6) months in advance. This would contribute to better team building and co-design processes.
- Clear and good instructions (e.g., a step-by-step process) available also in English to ensure accessibility, engagement and better understanding from all parties involved. Consider also opening webinars linked to specific calls as a communication tool.
- Include two-stage application processes, e.g., concept note and then proposal. This approach would also support co-design research.
- Foster flexible planning within research projects and allow flexibility in delivery timetables.
- Integrate contextual considerations that might help to foster knowledge co-development or motivate researchers from different contexts to join collaborative

initiatives between low-income and high-income countries, e.g., funders can visit project sites to better understand the context of project team members and beneficiaries so that calls reflect and balance different realities and priorities.

- Inclusion of explicit conditions that enable equity and fairness, e.g., 1) prerequisite to have a principal investigator in a partnering developing country, 2) pre-deadline for co-principal investigator, 3) include questions to assess how team projects will work with equity at all stages through the research project.
- Research agenda including topics, priorities, rules, methods need to be driven by researchers', practitioners', local agencies' and local communities' opinions, perspectives and needs and not driven by funders. Collaborative research proposals need to be connected to the needs of people involved in the research.
- Consider different types of products, factors or components to measure project societal impacts, scientific publications alone do not always capture all project results, reach key audiences (like policy makers, practitioners, beneficiaries) or represent different motivations within partnerships. Account for research outcomes but also non-research outputs.
- Be inclusive and support ideas from early career researchers or less experienced researchers. Evaluation should not only be based on principal investigator credibility or senior credits.
- Incorporate double blind reviews and interviews with applicants for clarifications.
- Providing good feedback for failed proposals would help to improve proposals for future applications and knowledge development in the long term.
- Involvement with researchers and open dialogue between funders and researchers could help understand each other's perspectives, problems, limitations and needs and create a space for new solutions and ideas.

Suggestions for funding allocation & utilization

- Allocation of funds need to be driven by the needs of researchers as well as the needs of direct and in-direct stakeholders of the research.
- Provide funding to create relations, networking and brainstorming sessions so that research proposals can emerge in more equal terms, e.g., "start-up network grant". Questions remain about how to implement this idea considering time allocation and salaries.
- Allow flexibility in budget items, flexible funding opportunities and access to a contingency budget would enhance more adaptable research processes to deal with emerging or unexpected issues. Sometimes creative accounting is needed to ensure a successful implementation of a project and more impactful results.
- Allow/include the use of seed money for co-designing proposals and collaborative writing, and ensure funds for researchers' mobility.
- Reevaluate/adjust restriction payments towards international collaboration to local contexts and conditions.

- Ensure a minimum percentage of the money to each collaborator, e.g., one PhD in each institution/country involved (one PhD - one PhD), one Postdoc in each institution/country involved (one Postdoc - one Postdoc).
- Implement the possibility for top up or follow up funds to support unforeseen circumstances or opportunities.
- Have more opportunities for project funds to support capacity building to build long term capacitated teams.
- Have more funds or funding opportunities for communication and dissemination activities as well as funds to follow-up research and implement project outcomes.
- Money for dissemination, not only extensions, which some projects cannot get, be more flexible for extension, considering context, e.g., people cannot collect data during some seasons like Ramadan.

Questions remain about how to help solve power dynamic issues within collaborative projects. Some ideas include that funders could consider different schemes to allocate and distribute funds, where universities involved in a research project, both from high-income and low-income countries, could have direct “partnership” with funders or where the main institutions involved could be receivers of funds.

Role of funders during project implementation

- Understand different situations, contexts, priorities, and changing needs.
- Help local authorities understand conditions for collaborative research, e.g., in relation to the use of money.
- Follow up money granted to projects.
- Integrate/ensure mobility possibilities to enhance knowledge co-production and capacity building.
- Project extensions should be available for good cause and more flexible.
- At the final stages, funders could even be more involved and provide support/guidance towards other types of funding that would help researchers implement the findings of the research.

Overall, practical experiences indicate that local contexts, beneficiaries’ perspectives and research needs should be taken into account, guide and play a significant role when defining and prioritizing the rules and topics of research proposals. Furthermore, participants highlighted that adding flexibility to research project grants would allow researchers to adjust the research proposals, methods, project activities or even project outcomes when needed, e.g., to better manage emerging issues, adapt to local context or changing needs. Mahajan et al. (2023) present similar reflections on adding flexibility to grants and research programs, which could positively support co-design processes within international collaborative collaborations.

Recommendations for international collaborative research projects

After digitizing the step-by-step posters and analyzing the pictorials drawn by each working group on workshop day 2, May 25th (see [Appendix A6](#)), the information was synthesized into key points for each research stage. The following subsections present the overall results of the SaR closing seminar as recommendations for each specific research stage. These guidelines are in alignment with the fundamental principles for fair, equitable and productive international collaborations presented above (Figure 1).

Stage 1. Developing the proposal and seeking/obtaining funding

This stage includes deciding on research topics, potential research partners, collaborators, research methods, etc.

- Effective leadership along with balanced and open dialogue, and honest communication.
- Involvement in the research including mobilization of the team, cultural sensitivity and local perspectives.
- Participation that entails team building while setting mutual expectations and a safe atmosphere. Be clear and explicit about expectations and motivations.
- Flexible planning with a clear timeline, detailed schedule and milestones.
- Sharing responsibilities within a respectful environment.
- Consolidation of a research proposal for funding that is jointly developed.

Stage 2. Startup of the research

This stage is about recruiting, initiating contact with communities and stakeholders, etc.

- Organize a kick off meeting: discuss the principles, bring everyone together, reassess the research proposal, create spaces to build trust and empathy.
- Clear distribution of roles, responsibilities and tasks in an open and transparent way.
- Assess the community's norms and values and reflect about access.
- Understand the local context and refine the project activities accordingly.
- When contacting communities and other stakeholders, be genuine, humble, and remember to respect differences.
- Compromise with all those involved in the project, including other researchers, communities, local authorities, other stakeholders while keeping your and the project's integrity.
- Communicate and disseminate at every stage of the project within the team and with participants.

Stage 3. On-going research

This stage entails data collection, fieldwork, sharing field data/input data, analysis phase and managing relationships with stakeholders, economic bureaucracy, receipts, bookings, per diems, etc.

- Regular follow-ups and one-on-one meetings with active listening and participation.
- Foster a culture of openness and honesty about conflict of interest, challenges and limitations, where everyone can share difficulties, ask for help and better understand why they are not delivering.
- Budget for contingencies or emerging opportunities, either within the project budgets or available as top-up/continuation grants.
- Take time for pre-fieldwork, piloting, testing, explaining the project and making field contacts – all need to understand the research and talk about ownership.
- Communicate timely about emerging problems.
- Foster interdisciplinary approaches. Be open to methodological feedback from the field (be adaptive) and have regular debrief sessions where principal investigators are also present.
- Ensure continuous learning and capacity building at all levels and stages (principal investigators, team members, field workers) - Build long term capacitated teams.
- Be responsible, transparent and accountable regarding project economy, resources and data.

N.B. Principal investigators should especially be aware and understand the large amount of time and energy needed to navigate admin and financial systems.

Stage 4. Closing phase - final stages

This final stage includes publishing, writing articles, reports to funders and others, handling co-authorships, and disseminating the results etc.

- Clear mutual agreements between project participants with respect to project products, milestones and timeline.
- Promote transparency and openness in all activities and project components including budget, authorship, data collection, delays, etc.
- Strategic planning including a clear roadmap (timeline) with milestones on budget, publications and other outputs (various stages, submission). Keep communication going at all levels.
- Work together to reach the milestones (co-production), ask for help and admit struggles, listen to each other, express expectations and remember to provide positive feedback.

These recommendations are available as a [checklist](#) that can be openly used, updated, improved and adapted to support future international collaborations.

Table 1. Frequency table of coded segments from answers to the question “What barriers have you encountered that hindered fair, productive and equitable research collaboration?”. This table shows the top topics/themes mentioned more than six times (n= 22 survey responses) within responses (see the full list of barriers in Appendix A4.3)

Coded responses	Frequency
Mobility restrictions, limited in-person meetings, & COVID	13
Unequal contributions to the process & papers	4
Limited communication & coordination	4
Time & geographic distance	4
Constraints imposed by current system	4

Forum Theater scenes overview

Scene representing research stage 1 - Group 1: Developing proposal and seeking/obtaining funding (Figure 3). *Challenges and social conflicts raised:*

- Power dynamics between universities from different countries and within team members.
- Disrespectful interactions among team members.
- Conflict of interests, different motivations.
- Lack of mutual understanding and communication.
- Funding agencies driving the priorities.

Figure 3. De-roling activity - scene on research stage 1. This scene was created and performed by participants in group 1 and facilitated by Elsa Sztaket. Working group 1: Asmamaw Alemu, Claudia Teutschbein, Emelie Adamsson, Halimu Suleiman Shauri, Harry Fischer, Henrik Pompeius, Liz Drury O’Neill, Gity Behravan, Marlino Eugénio Mubai, Örjan Bartholdson and Soundharajan Bankaru Swamy. Photo: Jineth Berrío-Martínez

Scene representing research stage 2 - Group 2: Startup of the research (Figure 4).

Challenges and social conflicts raised:

- Lack of contextual understanding that affects first contact with local communities, local authorities and beneficiaries.
- Differences in expectations, perceptions, motivations, priorities, personalities.
- Bureaucracy and lack of communication, lack of feedback to local communities and knowledge extractivism.
- Power dynamics and disrespectful treatment, assumptions linked to background.
- Chain of pressure across institutions and people.

Figure 4. De-roling activity - scene on research stage 2. This scene was created and performed by participants in group 2 and facilitated by Dactivo José Litsecuane Combane. Working group 2: Aroob Mohamed Alameen Alfaki, Emelie Rietz Liljedahl, Erik Karlton, Kasiviswanathan KS, Kristina Marquardt, Mattias Jonsson, Oskar Karlsson, Rubhana Raqib and Tim Daw. Photo: Jineth Berrío-Martínez

Scene representing research stage 3 - Group 3: On-going research (check-in meetings: first a simulated online meeting - Zoom call set-up, then in-person team meeting)

(Figure 5). Challenges and social conflicts raised:

- Lack of communication, connectivity issues, lack of trust and transparency.
- Project delays and non-deliveries from fieldwork, issues linked to data collection and data sharing despite having signed agreements.
- Language barriers, lack of mutual understanding and conflicts of interest.
- Different contexts, realities, needs, motivations, priorities, and difficulties resulting from this.
- Financial dependency and ethical issues.

Figure 5. Scene on research stage 3. This scene was created and performed by participants in group 3 and facilitated by Christopher Kazungu Cheupe. Working group 3: Almoayied Assayed, Daniel Munyao Mutyambai, Elin Stenfors, Emilie Lindkvist, Josepha Wessels, Maria Mancilla Garcia, Togbe Delano Tognizo Ronald. Photo: Jineth Berrío-Martínez

Scene representing research stage 4 - Group 4: Closing phase - final stages (Figure 6).
Challenges and social conflict raised:

- Previous delays implementing fieldwork and analyzing data as well as project deviation led to issues and discussion linked to expected outcomes, deliveries of the project and reports for funders.
- Lack of continuous communication, honest conversations, transparency, and trust among colleagues.
- Chain of pressure in relations to scientific publications. Pressures are transferable.
- Different motivations, priorities and expectations, unequal embedded structures.
- Unequal distribution of responsibilities, lack of sources to deal with emergent issues.

After each scene, the main issues depicted were jointly identified and discussed in plenary. Participants were asked to provide recommendations or potential solutions to change what they had perceived as problematic or uncomfortable. Questions such as “Which advice would you give others to think about/or do in these situations?” and “What needs to change for collaborations to be fairer and more productive?” were posted. Additionally, questions such as “Who needs to change what?” “What are the main obstacles to overcome?” and “What are the learnings?” were discussed. Participants were also given time to note down individual reflections and insights. This information was used to prepare the recommendations and suggestions included in this report.

Figure 6. Scene on research stage 4. This scene was created and performed by participants in group 3 and facilitated by Hanna Wetterstrand. Working group 4: Chandni, Christian Lindh, Fanny Christou, Freddy Soria, Libère Nkurunziza, Miriam Karlsson, Rosemarie Mwaipopo. Photo: Jineth Berrío-Martínez

Navigating the human relationships is even more important for these projects than I thought⁵

⁵ Participant's reflection - main take-away from the closing seminar May 24th-25th 2023 (workshop evaluation, response 13)

Final reflections

International research partnerships bring together researchers and stakeholders with different contexts, expertises, backgrounds, motivations, needs and opinions. According to the experiences from 13 granted research projects under the Sustainability and Resilience call 2018, there is a need to be more adaptive, equitable and inclusive, to take into account specific contexts, challenge assumptions and adopt systemic approaches in order deal with those challenges. Using reflections from Forum Theater scenes and participants' responses to the questions "What are your main take-aways from these two days?" some final reflections on Fair, Equitable and Productive International Collaborative Research are listed below:

- Effective communication, good time management and clearly defined roles and responsibilities through all stages in research are key aspects for successful projects and effective collaboration.
- There is a need to invest more time in building relationships and trust within international collaboration so that team members can get to know and learn from each other.
- Active listening, open discussions and allowing people to freely express ideas help develop mutual respect and understanding toward common goals.
- Thinking and talking explicitly about equality and fairness in research and multi-cultural discussions can be much more eye-opening but at the same time more demanding.
- Mutual understanding is crucial within collaborations as well as looking at the situation from different angles, there can be multiple perspectives of equity and fairness in the international research processes. Some power inequalities are not always obvious.
- Ongoing research processes implies building capacities, mutual understanding, and active engagement of all team members, which can be difficult to develop with a three-year project.

Seminar evaluation

We received 27 filled evaluation forms on the SaR closing seminar, representing 75% of workshop participants (some participants only attended one day or had to leave earlier). The evaluation form included five questions where people anonymously rated different workshop components using a 5-point scale: very poor, poor, neutral, good or great, two open questions to additional questions and main take-aways from the two-day workshop. Responses were transcribed and summarized in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Responses to the workshop evaluation questions. A total of 27 participants filled in the form. This bar plot is a direct representation of the transcribed answers. Green is very poor, gray is neutral, yellow is good, orange is great and pattern fill is NA. The “poor” option was not used by any participant

Overall, 17 and five participants, representing 63% and 18% of participants, felt that the workshop was great and good respectively, while other four participants (15%) felt neutral about the event and one person (4%) felt that it was very poor. Some participants commented on each question saying that it was a positive learning experience, “very nice activities” and creative methods that foster engagement with the topics, “strong enthusiasm and sense of importance”, “doing things and exchange ideas in a new approach”, “great planning” and “well organized”. On the other hand, one person said that more time could have been used “for refining our recommendations”.

Some participants also shared that it would have been good to “have a scientific session”, “know more about the research projects in addition to the very useful activities we have had” or “more time for scientific networking”. One reflected that “the focus could have been more on the scientific outputs”. These points were openly discussed in plenary, recognizing the main purpose of the seminar and the need for more time to discuss project results ([Link to project results’ posters](#)). One suggestion

for future events is to include oral presentations or exhibit short video clips of each project instead of posters, and allocate time in the agenda for knowledge-sharing activities. Therefore, if the purpose of a seminar is to focus on the research process and project results, it is highly recommended to plan for a longer event.

Partial group picture day 2 - Closing activity, May 25th 2023. Photo: Jineth Berrío-Martínez

It has been discussed enough during the seminar where exactly we lay and can make it more equitable, now it is about "acceptance". It is high time to realize what has been discussed in these two days and implement it wherever possible⁶

⁶ Participant's reflection - additional thoughts (workshop evaluation, response 10)

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Appendices

A1. Projects granted under the “Sustainability and Resilience” research program 2018⁷

1. Characterization of environmental pollution in Bangladesh by novel non-target mass spectrometry ‘exposomic’ analysis.
2. Forum Theatre to enhance joint agency in Kenya and Mozambique: towards relational understandings of climate change (FoRel).
3. Health impact of pesticide exposure in relation to climate change among populations in low- and middle-income countries.
4. Identifying, exploring, and preserving diversity of beneficial arthropods for sustainable tomato production.
5. Impacts of recent El-Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) on the Water-Food-Energy Nexus in South Asia.
6. Institutional networks and self-organized adaptation: Tracing the democratic architectures of climate response.
7. Market driven afforestation – trajectories in social resilience and environmental sustainability under land-use intensification.
8. Navigating the complexity of small-scale fishery interventions: An intersection of agent-based modeling and participatory empirical research (OctoPINTS).
9. Capacity building for aquaculture diversity and development: Increasing food security by improving resilience and productivity of smallholder aquaculture in the face of global change.
10. Resilience in Urban Sudan (RUS): An Interdisciplinary Spatial and Temporal Study of Social Cohesion and Resilience to tackle the consequences of Climate and Environmental Change in Urban Khartoum.
11. Sustaining fish and fishworkers? Human rights for migrant Burmese fishworkers in the EU-initiated sustainable fisheries reform in Thailand.
12. The practice of resilience in mountain landscapes: exploring risk and landscape investments in rural Nepal.
13. Towards sustainable maize production in East Africa: Cropping system resilience under climate change.
14. Transformational climate-smart options for sustainable agriculture and resilience on smallholder farms in areas with coarse-textured soils.
15. Wastewater treatment in small communities in Bolivia: Sustainable technologies and resilient planning.
16. Governing Climate Resilient Futures: gender, justice and conflict resolution in resource management.

[Link to the poster of project results’ outcomes shared during the closing seminar.](#)

⁷ <https://www.vr.se/english/applying-for-funding/decisions/2018-12-04-sustainability-and-resilience.html>

A2. Workshop Participants

The closing seminar participants, May 24th-25th 2023.

Full name	Affiliation	Project
Almoayied Assayed	Water, Environment & Climate Change Centre, Amman, Jordan	15
Ann Ericsson - Admin support	Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University	-
Aroob Mohamed Alameen Alfaki	University of Khartoum, Sudan	10
Asmamaw Alemu	University of Gondar	7
Chandni LNU	PhD student from India	5
Christian Lindh	Arbets och Miljömedicin, Lunds universitet	3
Christopher Kazungu Cheupe - Forum Theater facilitator	Wildlife Conservation Society, Kenya	2
Claudia Teutschbein	Uppsala University	5
Dactivo José Litsecuane Combane - Forum Theater facilitator	Eduardo Mondlane University, Mozambique	2
Daniel Munyao Mutyambai	International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, Nairobi, Kenya	13
Elin Stenfors	Uppsala University	5
Elsa Sztaket - Forum Theater facilitator	Dpt. of Teaching and Learning, Stockholm University	-
Emelie Adamsson (only May 24)	Vetenskapsrådet/ The Swedish Research Council (VR)	Funder
Emelie Rietz Liljedahl (only May 24)	Lund University	3
Emilie Lindkvist - organizer	Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden	8
Erik Karlton	Department of Soil and Environment, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	7
Eva Österlind - Forum Theater invited guest (only May 25)	Dpt. of Teaching and Learning, Stockholm University	-
Fanny Christou	Malmö University, Sweden	10
Freddy Soria	Catholic University of Bolivia	15
Gity Behravan (only May 24)	The Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (SIDA)	Funder

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Halimu Suleiman Shauri	Pwani University, Kenya	2
Hanna Wetterstrand - Lead facilitator	SwedBio at Stockholm Resilience Centre, Facilitator lead	-
Johannes Ernstberger - Photographer	Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University	-
Harry Fischer	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	6
Henrik Pompeius (only May 24)	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Funder
Jineth Berrío Martínez - Research assistant	Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University	8
Josepha Wessels	Malmö University, Sweden	10
Kasiviswanathan KS	Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee, India	5
Kristina Marquardt	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	12
Libère Nkurunziza	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	14
Liz Drury O'Neill - Organizer	Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University	8,2
Maria Mancilla Garcia - Organizer	Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University and the Free University of Brussels, Brussels	2
Marlino Eugénio Mubai	Eduardo Mondlane University, Mozambique	2
Mattias Jonsson	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	13
Miriam Karlsson	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	4
Örjan Bartholdson	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	12
Oskar Karlsson	Stockholm University	1
Rosemarie Mwaipopo	University of Dar es Salaam, Tanzania	8
Rubhana Raqib	International Centre for Diarrhoeal Disease Research, Bangladesh (icddr,b)	1
Soundharajan Bankaru Swamy	Nexus in South Asia	5
Tamihda Ahmed - Trainee/workshop assistant	Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University	-
Tim Daw - Organizer	Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University	2,8
Togbe Delano Tognizo Ronald	Int. Institute of Tropical Agriculture IITA-Benin	4

A3. Digitized action points from Start-up seminar 2019

Table A3. List of key issues and action points identified during the Start-up seminar in 2019. Digitized information from pictures of the five Solutions posters in the report (Drury O’Neill et al. 2019)

Summary issue	Poster	Analysis of why it is an issue	Action points i.e., who should do what
Ensuring equality/trust/respect/openness within the research team and process (Fig. 3)	<p>Research team (in)equality</p>	<p>Financial/salary/infrastructure Power structures/hierarchy/gender Perception of knowledge: <i>hampers development of capacity in both ways and reduces quality of research</i></p>	<p>ACTION POINTS TEAMS Team meeting in partner countries > diffuse power relations Project/partnership agreements (define roles, contributions, communication...) as a live document Presenting contributions by all team members regardless of title/academic status (reading groups) Foster transparency: constructive feedback, honesty, dialogue when disagreement Risk analysis together Project management agreed objectives Ownership of data/analysis End of project: sharing results/presentation at international platforms north and south mode by all team members</p> <p>ACTION POINTS FUNDERS - Co-funding from partner countries - Ensure capacity building in both directions (from “AID” to “COOPERATION”)</p>
Dealing with disparities in scientific resources/ Inequality of resources (Fig. 4)	<p>Inequality of resources and what can southern institutions do? – to foster productive collaborations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resources e.g., internet, journals, equipment, statistical packages for analysis - Research projects not linked to needed infrastructure - Lack of capacity of southern institutions to implement research in totality - Lack of researchers/students in specialist disciplines - Research projects linked to infrastructure investment - S. institutions to ensure N. partners harmonize & avoid duplication - Strategically use o/heads to strengthen S. institutions 	<p>S. INSTITUTIONS to have guidelines or protocol for engagement e.g.,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storage & access to data - Compensation for staff time - Consideration of sustainability of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Capacity * Knowledge * Tools * Ideas for future res & curricula * Stakeholder engagement

Summary issue	Poster	Analysis of why it is an issue	Action points i.e., who should do what
Freedom and risks in research on politically sensitive issues (Fig. 5)	<p>Issues and risks of politically & socially sensitive research</p>	<p>SUMMARY</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Poor knowledge of political contexts e.g., exposing masculinities, the state & resource management Minimal appreciation of how politics influence research e.g., "No GMOs!!" <p>ANALYSIS:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Interference in research process Jeopardizing southern partners <p>Quality of research findings (To say? or not say?)</p>	<p>ALL RESEARCH PARTIES</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> "Grounding" – politics of the times Publications - "Packaging messages" South has to lead the process
Knowledge exchange, actionability and feedback of research (Fig. 6)	<p>Knowledge exchange, actionability and feedback of results</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Differential interests among stakeholders and researchers Dissemination methodologies Involvement & participation of research subjects in the design of projects Fragmentation of knowledge/resources researchers 	<p>SOLUTIONS/- ACTION POINTS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Identification and prioritization of interest & needs</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1.1 Identify the different levels of stakeholders</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tailor outputs to those needs (Researchers, stakeholders, ??) - Differential delivery of results <i>2. Tailor make delivery methods</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Figure out from the very beginning on feedbacking <i>3. Create opportunities for involvement & participation</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Actualize IT? (Researchers, stakeholders, ??) <i>4. Build trust, respect & transparency of dealings</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Invest in social/soft skills - Exchange visits - Guest professorships - Informal engagements (Researchers, funders institutions, Universities)

Summary issue	Poster	Analysis of why it is an issue	Action points i.e., who should do what
<p>Achieving fair and effective communication from start to finish (Fig. 7)</p>	<p>Fair and effective communication in international collaborative research</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human/soft issues: offense, misunderstandings, conflicts, deviation? - Intersectionality: gender, culture, norm, seniority, inter-relations - Technical: language, internet speed, time differences, channels of communication, effective 	<p>Prepare and share agenda collaboratively</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Planning together in groups, in person - Communication evolves... talk about the issues to address that - Agreement on the best way of communicating => agree of the beginning * Openness, discuss potential conflicts, problems * Let people know when you are not able to communicate * Revisit and evaluate communication modes different stages <p>Sense of belonging smaller ideas into the big project design</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feedback is very important => increase dedication - Awareness of other disciplinary languages - Consider different channels for different topics - Common calendar * Importance of body language and facial expression * Monthly meetings online conference and yearly meetings face to face * Use online collaborative platforms? e.g., slack, other apps...<i>Meeting minutes</i>

A4. Pre-workshop survey results

Frequency tables of coded segments per question⁸.

A4.1. Valuable insights about fair and equitable international collaborative research through the process of your VR/SaR project (n= 22 survey responses)

Coded responses	Frequency
Inclusive & collaborative process at all stages	11
Outcomes from this collaborative process	9
Integrating diverse perspectives and expertise	9
Effective collaboration, cooperation and active participation	9
Having time & means for building partnerships	6
Effective collaboration, cooperation and active participation	5
Awareness of contextual differences	4
Clearly defined roles, responsibilities, tasks	4
Clear, open and transparent communication	4
Efficient and structured project management	4
Co-creation & co-production knowledge	4
Continuous learning from the project implementation & outcomes	4
Common interest, understanding, goals and incentives	3
Constraints imposed by current system	3
Clarity in collaboration agreements	3
Establishing/sharing expectations, priorities	2
Mutual respect and trust	2
More collaborative projects are needed	2
Avoid implicit assumptions	2
Handling power imbalances	2
(Un)Fair and equitable distribution/implementation of resources	2
Other topics	8

⁸ Answers to the pre-workshop survey sent to participants before arrival were thematically coded through an iterative process using MAXQDA (VERBI Software, 2019).

A4.2. Key factors that contribute to fair, productive and equitable research collaboration (n= 22 survey responses)

Coded responses	Frequency
Inclusive & collaborative process at all stages	8
Clear, open and transparent communication	7
Clearly defined roles, responsibilities, tasks	5
Mutual respect and trust	5
Common interest, understanding, goals and incentives	4
Efficient teamwork	4
Regular team meetings (monthly) & 1-1 dialogue	4
Providing equal opportunities for contribution	3
Ability to be flexible and adaptive	3
Establishing/sharing expectations, priorities	3
Having more effective & long term funding	3
Outcomes from this collaborative process	3
Effective collaboration, cooperation and active participation	3
Awareness of contextual differences	2
Encourage the counterpart to take the lead	2
Ability awareness & willingness to share	2
Complementary team	2
Transparent & clear authorship guidelines	2
Document team meetings & follow up	2
Integrating diverse perspectives and expertise	2
Having time & means for building partnerships	2
(Un)Fair and equitable distribution/implementation of resources	2
Simple collaboration agreements	1
Other topics	7

A4.3. Key barriers that hinder fair, productive and equitable research collaboration (n= 22 survey responses)

Coded responses	Frequency
Mobility restrictions, limited in-person meetings, & COVID	13
Unequal contributions to the process & papers	4
Limited communication & coordination	4
Time & geographic distance	4
Constraints imposed by current system	4
Limited budget for research projects	3
Non delivery of project outputs/research under-delivers	3
Funding/financial dependency	3
Cultural barriers, working and communication styles	2
Language barriers	2
Lack of mutual understanding	2
Lack of time for building partnerships	2
Short-term projects	2
None barriers	2
Internal administrative structure	2
Frequency of project reports	1
Limited time for co-design process	1
Delayed signing/reaching agreements	1
Only one partner have control over funds & research	1
Lack of work recognition	1
Imbalance between available resources and project goals	1
Technical constraints	1
Different incentives	1
Project interdependencies	1
Other topics	4

A5. Summarized agenda day 1 & day 2

When	Activity details DAY 1 – Wednesday May 24 th , 2023
08:45	Start-up and registration: Coffee mingle and viewing the project results' posters
09:30	Who are we in the room? Interactive exercises to get to know each other
09:50	Presentations: <i>What were the conclusions from the start-up seminar in 2019, and the pre-workshop survey results linked to this closing seminar?</i>
10.05	What will we do during these two days? Proposed agenda and collectively agreeing on rules of engagement for the two-day seminar - Chatham house rules
10:40	<i>Break: Coffee and fruit</i>
10:45	Individual reflection: <i>What does equitable and fair research collaboration between high income countries and low/middle income countries mean to you?</i>
11:05	Introducing thinking pairs exercise
11:20	Thinking pairs exercise: <i>What assumptions might researchers make that hinders them from doing fair and equitable international collaborative research projects?</i>
11:55	<i>Break: Coffee and fruit</i>
12:00	Plenary activity: What are insights or highlights from the pairs?
12:10	Group exercise: What is most important to consider for each specific research stage? (Four research phases/eight working groups)
12:30	<i>Lunch at Proviant Albano - Group picture 1</i>
13:35	Presentation & warming up for Forum Theater: What is Forum Theater and where does it come from? & Example of scene
14:30	Group exercise: Script development for each specific research stage in <i>international collaborative research projects</i> – four groups
15:15	<i>Coffee break: snack and fruits</i>
15:25	Scene 1: 1st group performs the scene representing common situations when developing a collaborative research proposal and seeking/obtaining funding (stage 1) - reflection
15:55	Individual reflection on a scene: <i>What would you recommend others to think about/or do in this stage of a collaborative international project? What needs to change for collaborations to be fairer, more equitable and productive? What are the learnings from this scene?</i>
16.05	Thinking council exercise: Short presentation from a funding agency & Coffee groups: How can funders contribute to equitable and fair international research collaboration?
16:50	Finalization of the day: What have you appreciated today?
16:55	<i>Time for viewing the project results' posters and networking (group walk)</i>
18:00	<i>Workshop Dinner at CAROLAS EKO</i>

When	Activity details DAY 2 – Thursday May 25 th , 2023
09:10	Recap and plan for today
09:30	Warming up & getting ready to perform – coffee station
10.00	Scene 2: 2nd group performs the scene representing common situations when starting up a collaborative international research project (stage 2) - reflections & learnings
10.30	Scene 3: 3rd group performs the scene representing common situations when implementing a collaborative international project - “on-going research” (stage 3) - reflections & learnings
11.00	Scene 4: 4th group performs the scene representing common situations when closing a collaborative international research project - “final stages” (stage 4) - reflections & learnings
11:30	<i>Coffee break: snack and fruits</i>
12:00	Plenary discussion & Group exercise and pictorial analysis introduction
12.30	<i>Lunch at Proviant Albano</i>
13.30	Group exercise: 1) What would be the guiding principles according to you to ensure equitable and fair international research collaboration? Identify guiding principles for each specific research stage - six working groups. 2) How to guide a researcher to do fair, productive and equitable international research collaboration? Prepare a step-by-step guide on posters .
15.20	<i>Coffee break: bullar and fruits – Group picture 2</i>
15:35	Refining the step-by-step posters, time to visit and contribute to other posters Workshop evaluation
16:15	Round of appreciation of the two days Closing words and how to move forward (volunteer sign-up)

A6. Step-by-step posters: Guiding principles and guidelines for research stage per working group

[Link to the pictures of the step-by-step posters](#)

STAGE 1 - theme: Developing proposal and seeking/obtaining funding (i.e., deciding research topic, who to apply together with, collaborators, research methods, etc.)

STAGE 2 - theme: Startup of the research (i.e. recruiting initiating contact with communities and stakeholders)

STAGE 3 - theme: On-going research (i.e. data collection, fieldwork, sharing field data/input data analysis phase and managing relationships with stakeholders, economic bureaucracy of financial reports, receipts, bookings, per diems etc.)

STAGE 4 - theme: Final stages (i.e. publishing, writing articles, reports to funders and others, handling co-authorships, and disseminating the results etc.)

